

PSYCHOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF SPIRITUAL-MORAL EDUCATION

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Аннотация

Ушбу мақолада маънавий-ахлоқий тарбия тушунчаси, унинг мазмун-моҳияти, психологик механизмлари ҳамда инсон ривожланишидаги ўрни таҳлил қилинади. Маънавий ва ахлоқий кадрларни шакллантириш жараёнида ижтимоий муҳит, оила, таълим муассасалари ва шахсинг индивидуал хусусиятлари қандай таъсир кўрсатиши ёритилади. Шунингдек, шахсий онг, тафаккур, ҳис-туйғулар ва тажриба орқали ахлоқий қарашларнинг шаклланишига оид илмий ёндашувлар кўриб чиқилади.

Калит сўзлар: маънавий тарбия, ахлоқий кадрлар, шахс ривожланиши, психологик механизмлар, ижтимоий муҳит, онг, эмпатия, ички назорат.

Аннотация

В статье анализируется понятие духовно-нравственного воспитания, его сущность, психологические механизмы и его роль в развитии человека. На формирование духовно-нравственных ценностей оказывают влияние социальная среда, семья, образовательные учреждения и индивидуальные особенности человека. Также рассматриваются научные подходы к формированию нравственных взглядов посредством сознания, мышления, эмоций и опыта личности.

Ключевые слова: духовное воспитание, нравственные ценности, развитие личности, психологические механизмы, социальная среда, сознание, эмпатия, внутренний контроль.

Abstract

This article analyzes the concept of spiritual and moral education, its essence, psychological mechanisms, and its role in human development. The social environment, family, educational institutions and individual characteristics of a person influence the formation of spiritual and moral values. Also, scientific approaches to the formation of moral views through personal consciousness, thinking, emotions and experience are considered.

Key words: spiritual education, moral values, personality development, psychological mechanisms, social environment, consciousness, empathy, internal control.

Spiritual and moral education is a complex and continuous process of upbringing aimed at bringing a person to spiritual, moral, social and moral perfection. It plays an important role in the full formation of a person's personality, determining his place and purpose in life, and functioning in society in a worthy and effective way. Through spiritual and moral education, good feelings, high human virtues such as justice, fairness, conscience, compassion and responsibility are formed in the human heart and mind. This process helps a person to understand the truth, strive to respect himself and others, and adhere to spiritual norms in life. At the same time, spiritual and moral education directs a person to cooperation in society, to help each other, and to express himself positively.

This form of education should be analyzed not only from a philosophical and social point of view, but also from a psychological point of view. Because the spiritual and moral development of a person is closely related to his inner world - his feelings, thinking, aspirations and ability to understand himself. In psychology, spiritual and moral development is realized through the formation

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of an internal control mechanism in a person, the development of the ability to empathize and the conscious acceptance of social values [1].

Spiritual and moral education educates not only the external behavior of a person, but also his internal psychological state. Through such education, a person not only develops the ability to observe moral norms, but also learns to feel responsible for his behavior, not to harm others, and to adhere to the principles of humanity and justice in any situation.

For spiritual and moral education to be effective, close cooperation between social institutions such as the family, school, society and the media is necessary. The personal example of parents, the moral qualities of teachers, and the general spiritual environment in society have a significant impact on the spiritual growth of a person.

Spiritual and moral education is one of the main conditions necessary for a person to achieve spiritual perfection, to function adequately in society, and to faithfully fulfill his duty as a human being. Through a deep psychological analysis of this process, it is possible to understand its essence and increase its effectiveness. Spirituality is the basis of noble feelings, universal human values, and personal philosophy formed in the human mind. It serves as the main criterion for a person to understand his goals, duty, and responsibility in life. Morality is the practical expression of these spiritual foundations in everyday life. That is, how a person thinks on a spiritual basis, and how he expresses those thoughts in moral terms. This process is, first of all, closely related to the development of human consciousness, its empathy (the ability to understand and feel others), internal control (the ability to control one's own behavior), and social cognitive abilities (the ability to understand and evaluate relationships in society). In psychology, such abilities are considered as one of the decisive factors in the spiritual and moral growth of a person. Also, spiritual and moral education is a continuous process that continues throughout a person's life, starting from childhood. It is founded in the family environment, strengthened in educational institutions and enriched by various influences in society. If this process is supported in every way, a person will mature not only as an educated, but also as a spiritually mature and morally pure person.

Spiritual and moral education forms a person's personal position and helps him realize his responsibility towards his life and society. The formation of spiritual perfection in a person ensures that he acts based on principles such as justice, honesty and integrity in his life decisions. From a psychological point of view, spiritual and moral education develops in a person the abilities of inner awareness, reflection and self-evaluation. Creating an environment enriched with spiritual ideas in the process of education and upbringing creates the basis for the formation of positive behavior and a position that benefits society in children. If a person has a high level of spiritual and moral stability, he can behave correctly and avoid bad habits, regardless of external influences.

From a psychological perspective, a person's moral development progresses in stages. This development begins in childhood when a person draws conclusions and regulates his behavior based on external influences. Over time, he learns to act on the basis of social relationships, social rules, and universal human values. According to psychological analyses, a person's moral maturity is closely related to the development of his consciousness, thinking, and internal control.

Psychologist Lawrence Kohlberg's theory of moral development provides a more in-depth understanding of this process. According to his definition, moral development includes three main stages and six substages:

- Preconventional stage (preconventional): At this stage, a person (usually a child) makes moral decisions based on punishment or reward. The concept of good and bad is based on external

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consequences. For example, for a child, 'good' is associated with avoiding punishment, and 'bad' is associated with receiving punishment.

- Conventional stage: At this stage, a person tries to comply with the norms of society. It becomes important for him to be respected by society, maintain social status, and act in accordance with the moral standards accepted in the community. In this case, being a 'good person', being approved by those around him, becomes the main goal of the person.
- Post-conventional stage: At this stage, a person acquires the ability to think independently morally. He understands universal human values, makes decisions based on inner convictions and conscience. For a person at this level, concepts such as justice, human rights, and freedom are of primary importance. He does not blindly follow the rules of society, but critically analyzes them and independently forms his own views.

As stated by Kohlberg, thinking ability, reflection (awareness of one's own behavior), empathy and internal control play an important role in the moral growth of a person. These are the main mechanisms of human moral decision-making [2]. Therefore, in the process of spiritual and moral education, it is necessary to pay serious attention not only to the teaching of moral rules, but also to the thinking and emotional development of the individual. For this purpose, it is recommended to use analysis of problematic situations, discussion of unregistered moral issues, dramatization, debate and psychological training in educational institutions.

The role of the family in spiritual education is invaluable - the child acquires the first moral concepts through parents and relatives. Schools and educational institutions systematically continue this process, forming humanism, patriotism and cultural tolerance.

The sense of empathy and internal control, which are considered important in psychology, play a decisive role in the spiritual and moral development of a person. Empathy is the ability to understand the feelings of others and feel their state, which encourages a person to compassion, understanding and tolerance. Internal control is based on a person's ability to control their own feelings, passions and actions, to direct themselves correctly and feel responsible. These feelings are of immense importance in the formation of human relationships, mutual respect and social responsibility.

These characteristics serve to educate a person not only morally, but also as a mature person who can establish effective and stable relationships in society. Therefore, it is very important to stimulate thinking, form the ability to understand oneself, and use methods based on reflection in the educational and upbringing processes. For example, in the process of educational work with children and adolescents, methods such as discussing moral problems, analyzing life events, and teaching them to express their feelings and thoughts affect the inner world of a person[3]. This way, they develop the ability to approach situations independently and humanely. Such an approach serves as a key factor in psychological maturity, spiritual maturity, and moral independence. In modern society, negative trends such as spiritual weakness, moral crisis, and individualism are widespread. These problems can negatively affect a person's inner world and disrupt their activity in social relations and moral views. Therefore, effective struggle against such problems is becoming an urgent task for every society.

In this regard, psychological trainings and practical exercises based on moral analysis are of great importance. Through psychological exercises, a person develops empathy, responsibility, internal control and self-awareness. Moral analysis helps to study the moral aspects of various life situations and form non-state approaches to problems.

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Also, in the process of spiritual and moral education, it is very important to establish strong cooperation between the family and the school. Moral knowledge and values instilled in the family are strengthened in the school environment, creating a solid foundation for the personal and social development of the child. At school, universal human values are promoted through educational activities, moral lessons and public events.

The successful implementation of spiritual and moral education not only contributes to the formation of a person as a harmonious, responsible and spiritually mature person, but also to the establishment of a stable and healthy spiritual environment in society. This serves as an important factor in ensuring the overall development and well-being of society.

Spiritual and moral education plays a very important role in the development of the human personality. A clear understanding of its psychological foundations and their correct application in practice significantly increases the effectiveness of the educational process. Also, the formation of human virtues occurs through the interrelation of values such as compassion, responsibility, justice and conscience. This process depends on the joint and coordinated activities of the family, school, society and psychological support systems. Every child and young person needs a decent and supportive environment for spiritual development.

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